

Inclusive Educational Practices in Childcare Settings: Perspective of Parents of Children with Special Needs

Pratiques éducatives inclusives en milieux de garde : perspective des parents d'enfants ayant des besoins particuliers

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Abstract

Background. While the benefits of including children with special needs in an educational childcare program are widely recognized for the children, their peers and their parents or caregivers, the approach calls for flexibility. It is also essential to consider the parents' perspective and involve them in their child's inclusion. However, there is little published information on parents' view of childcare, especially as regards children with special needs. The present article helps correct this information gap by documenting parents' perspective on the inclusive educational practices implemented by the educational childcare program in Quebec.

Method. For purposes of this study, relevant information was collected from 76 parents of children with special needs based on a large-scale online Quebec survey. Three research objectives aimed to determine if parents: 1) approved of the adaptation measures implemented in the childcare setting; 2) agreed with the identification of their children's developmental needs; and 3) agreed that their children's inclusion experience was a positive one. Descriptive statistics were used to quantify responses.

Results. Seventy-four percent of parents agreed or strongly agreed that their children's developmental needs had been correctly identified. Sixty percent or more acknowledged that available materials, instructions and individual interventions were adequate, confirming that the childcare setting

implemented diverse adaptation measures to meet the specific needs of their children. Finally, parents' responses indicated that they are involved in their children's inclusion, with 75% agreeing or strongly agreeing that the inclusion experience in the childcare setting was a positive one.

Conclusion. *Although preliminary, this study paints a portrait of certain educational practices in childcare settings attended by children with disabilities. Our findings highlight the importance of individualized practices and parental involvement to improve the inclusion experience for children with special needs in Quebec childcare settings.*

Résumé

Contexte. Bien que les avantages de l'inclusion des enfants ayant des besoins particuliers (BP) en milieux de garde soient largement reconnus pour ces enfants, leurs pairs, leurs parents ou les personnes qui s'en occupent, celle-ci exige une certaine flexibilité. Il est essentiel de prendre en compte la perspective des parents et de les impliquer dans l'inclusion de leur enfant. Il existe peu d'informations sur leur point de vue quant aux milieux de garde, en particulier pour les enfants BP. Le présent article documente donc leur perspective à l'égard des pratiques éducatives inclusives mises en œuvre par les milieux de garde au Québec.

Méthode. Nous avons recueilli des données auprès de 76 parents d'enfants BP dans le cadre d'une vaste enquête provinciale menée en ligne. L'étude poursuit trois objectifs, soit de déterminer si les parents : 1) approuvaient les mesures d'adaptation mises en œuvre dans le milieu de garde ; 2) étaient d'accord sur l'identification des besoins de développement de leur enfant; et 3) étaient d'accord pour dire que l'expérience d'inclusion de leur enfant était positive. Des statistiques descriptives ont été utilisées pour analyser les données.

Résultats. Plus de 60 % des parents ont reconnu que le matériel disponible, les instructions et les interventions individuelles étaient adéquats, ce qui corrobore le fait que le milieu de garde a adopté diverses mesures d'adaptation répondant aux besoins spécifiques de leur enfant ; 74% étaient d'accord ou tout à fait d'accord pour dire que les besoins de développement de leur enfant avaient été correctement identifiés. Enfin, les réponses des parents indiquent qu'ils ont participé à l'inclusion de leur enfant, dont 75 % d'entre eux sont d'accord ou tout à fait d'accord pour dire que l'expérience d'inclusion dans le milieu de garde était positive.

Conclusion. Bien que préliminaire, cette étude dresse un portrait de certaines pratiques éducatives en milieu de garde auprès des enfants BP. Les résultats mettent de l'avant l'importance de l'individualisation des pratiques et de l'implication des parents pour améliorer l'expérience d'inclusion des enfants BP dans les milieux de garde au Québec.

Mots clés : parents, enfants avec besoins particuliers, enfants handicapés, milieu de garde

Introduction

In Canada, each province and territory is responsible for policies on educational childcare. The Government of Quebec in 1997 developed a network of childcare services accessible to all children from birth to age 5 that differs from that in other provinces and territories (ministère de la Famille [MFA], 2019b). This network consists of *centres de la petite enfance* (CPE), subsidized and non-subsidized childcare centres as well as family childcare providers recognized by a coordinating office. The cost of attending a childcare centre is subsidized for the majority of centres with the exception of those that are non-subsidized. Subsidized centres offer reduced fee spaces, currently at a single rate of \$8.70 per day. The cost of attending a non-subsidized centre varies with each one. However, non-subsidized childcare centres offer spaces that qualify for the childcare tax credit (MFA, 2019b). This universal program aims, among other things, to promote equal opportunity for children's development (Bigras & Lemay, 2012).

In 2016, over half of young children (5 years old and under) in Quebec (i.e., 267,127) were enrolled in an educational childcare program, whether a CPE, subsidized or unsubsidized childcare, or a family childcare setting (MFA, 2019a). Some of these children were typically developing while others presented with special needs, meaning they required additional support for a variety of reasons including a physical, sensory or intellectual disability, a developmental disorder, an attention deficit or oppositional disorder, or a language or learning disability (Deslauriers, 2018). Although the inclusion of children with special needs is known to benefit them in many ways (e.g., gains in overall development, increase in social interactions, social adaptation, etc.; Gauvreau, 2019; Odom et al., 2006; Warrena et al., 2016; Wolery & Hemmeter, 2011), the approach calls for great flexibility and a variety of accommodations in childcare settings.

To encourage the acceptance of children with special needs in childcare settings, the Government of Quebec created various guidance documents and measures, among them the 2001 *Guide pour faciliter l'action concertée en matière d'intégration des enfants handicapés dans les services de garde du Québec* in consultation with the ministère de la Famille et de l'Enfance, the ministère de la Santé et des Services sociaux, the ministère de l'Éducation et l'Office des personnes handicapées du Québec (Comité provincial sur l'intégration des enfants handicapés dans les services de garde, 2001). This guide serves as a reference tool for the various people and organizations involved. Additionally, since 1977, various management, development, equipment or operating costs are covered by the Allowance for Integrating a Disabled Child aged 59 months or younger into Educational Childcare (ministère de la Famille et des Aînés 2012). And in 2004, financial assistance for the integration of children with disabilities in childcare settings was made available by the ministère de la Famille together with the ministère de la Santé et des Services sociaux (ministère de la Famille, 2015). This measure offers financial support to childcare services to enable them to accommodate children with special needs and reduce the barriers hindering their inclusion. These measures partly explain why the number of these children in daycare settings has increased. Indeed, the total number of children with special needs has more than tripled in recent years, rising from 2,383 in 2003-2004 (Office des personnes handicapées du Québec [OPHQ], 2007) to about 9,000 in 2016-2017 (MFA, 2018).

The following section emphasizes the importance of inclusive educational practices for all children, with or without special needs, in educational childcare and explains the necessity of

involving their parents in the process. Toward this end, the study focuses on parents' perspective to determine if they 1) approved of the adaptation measures implemented in the childcare setting; 2) agreed about the identification of their children's developmental needs; and 3) agreed that the inclusion experience for their children was a positive one.

Children with Special Needs

If children with special needs are to participate in childcare activities, they must be given special attention. The implementation of inclusive educational activities adapted to all children is essential. Such activities must be adapted to children with special needs, so that they as well as their peers can function in a mainstream environment despite the environment's difficulty to include them. In 2016, 42.3% of parents of children 5 years old and less reported having at least one child with a health or developmental problem (e.g., language impairment, autism spectrum disorder [ASD], attention deficit disorder [ADD], anxiety disorder, physical disability or chronic health problem, global developmental delay; Lavoie & Fontaine, 2016). In line with the various diagnoses, the practices employed in childcare settings must be individualized to each child's needs. To illustrate, Deris and Di Carlo (2013) recall that the use of multiple modalities (auditory, visual, tactile) emphasizing the strengths of these children improves their chances of functioning well in a mainstream environment. Childcare staff are responsible for implementing educational practices for each child with special needs. Accordingly, the perceptions of parents must be addressed so they can better support their child's inclusion (Kendall, 2019).

Inclusive Educational Childcare

Childcare settings that welcome children with special needs do so voluntarily, as this is not an obligation. In 2015-2016, 3,424 out of 17,805 such programs accepted children with special needs, representing less than a fifth of all educational childcare services (19%; OPHQ, 2017). These programs fully involve these children and enable them to live and grow as part of their community and receive the services they require (MFA, 2019b). They offer them the chance to participate in group activities to the extent possible, develop a sense of belonging, and establish interpersonal relations with both their peers and the staff (Hebbel Spiker, 2016). Moreover, the MFA (2019b) notes that "the education of young children must be based on methods and strategies that are respectful and adapted to their ways of learning and developing" (p. 7) (free translation). Thus, in a high-quality inclusive program, the staff take into account each child's individual abilities and needs (Bigras & Gagné, 2016).

Although children with special needs can greatly benefit from participation in a high-quality inclusive program (Nahmias et al., 2014), the development and implementation of such programs face many barriers (e.g., lack of training and staff concerns; Point & Desmarais, 2011). Indeed, the educational interventions involved call for personnel who are highly sensitive to the children's experience, needs, communication and learning (MFA, 2019b). Thus, rather than emphasize the difference between children with special needs and their peers, the staff will provide a continuum of strategies and an intensity of interventions to meet each child's individual and developmental needs (Guralnick & Bruder, 2016). Hemmeter et al, (2015) support use of the same learning activity to meet the different needs of each child via differentiated intervention strategies.

Educational Practices and Parental Involvement

Attendance alone is not enough to develop these children's potential (Strain et al., 2011); certain practices must also be employed to help them benefit fully from the learning opportunities offered (Sandall et al., 2019). Such practices include the use of visual aids (Chen et al., 2012; Gauvreau, 2019; Goldenberg et al., 2013), adapted materials and instructions (Brodzeller et al., 2018), modifications of the physical environment and arrangements regarding schedule and activities (Beaupré et al., 2017; Brodzeller et al., 2018; McWilliam et al., 2001; Poon & Yang, 2016). Adapted environments allow children with special needs to develop socially and acquire new competencies, thereby preventing behaviour problems before they start (Hebbeler & Spiker, 2016).

In addition to educational practices supporting the inclusion of all children, practices encouraging the involvement of parents of children with special needs must be put in place (Cantin et al., 2010). Some authors insist, notably, on the importance of asking for parents' input when identifying the child's needs (Dionne et al., 2014) and implementing communication practices that promote collaboration, reciprocity and shared decision-making between parents and childcare staff (Forry et al., 2011; Sheridan et al., 2010; Trivette et al., 2010). Indeed, parents should be recognized as experts on their children and represent a valuable resource (Flamant et al., 2011; Wetherby et al., 2021). As a result, a consideration of their perspective appears essential to ensure their satisfaction with the child services offered. Among the factors likely to influence parents' satisfaction, those most often mentioned include access to services for the child, information, quality of services and adaptation of educational practices (Bourke-Taylor et al., 2012; Cappe, 2012). The present study therefore proposes to examine the perspective of parents of children with special needs as regards the inclusive educational practices used in their child's educational childcare setting.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine if parents: 1) approved of the adaptation measures implemented in the childcare setting; 2) agreed on the identification of their children's developmental needs; and 3) agreed that the inclusion experience for their children was a positive one. The research project was approved by the human ethics research committee of the Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières and of the organizations concerned (CER-18-252-07.21 and CÉRP-2018-018-00). Note that this article is part of a larger-scale project aimed at developing, implementing and evaluating a model supporting the overall development of children in inclusive childcare programs (Dionne et al., 2017-2024).

Materials and Methods

Participants

The sample is part of a large-scale provincial survey on inclusion in childcare settings that involved the participation of 1,446 respondents from all regions of Quebec. Of these, 113 were parents of children with special needs. Table 1 presents the main sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents.

For the purposes of this study, only data for parents who had children with special needs in childcare programs and who answered all questions were included ($N = 76/113$; 67%). The respondents represented 15 of the 17 administrative regions in Quebec. Almost all respondents were mothers (94.7%). The majority were between 30 and 39 years old (84.2%), and slightly more than half had a university degree (56.6%). Children of the respondents presented many difficulties including language impairments, autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disability or global developmental disorder, physical disability, sensory disability, neglect or youth protection or others (e.g., allergies, pulmonary impairment, epilepsy, digestive illness, Tourette syndrome, attachment disorder and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder).

Table 1

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants and their Children (N = 76)

Characteristics	<i>n</i>	%
Parents' age (years)		
16-19	0	0
20-29	5	6.6
30-39	64	84.2
40-49	6	7.9
50-59	1	1.3
60 and over	0	0
Level of schooling		
Secondary school partially completed	1	1.3
Diploma of secondary studies	2	2.6
Diploma of professional studies	6	7.9
College studies partially completed	6	7.9
Diploma of college studies	9	11.8
University studies partially completed	9	11.8
University degree	43	56.6
Language spoken at home		
French	74	97.4
English	2	2.6

Procedures

The large-scale survey was promoted between March and June 2019 using several dissemination strategies that included its presentation on different websites and social networks of organizations (e.g., early childhood organizations, various professional associations, parents of children with disabilities, CPE, professional conferences in psychoeducation, psychology, teaching, etc.). Interested parents were directed to the project's website, which offered further information about the research and how to access the survey.

Measurement Tools

The provincial survey consisted of nine self-report questionnaires developed by the research team. Each questionnaire addressed one type of respondent as follows (for additional information on the method used, see Dionne et al., 2020):

- Childcare setting: 1) directors, 2) educational staff
- School setting: 3) directors; 4) school staff
- Specialized services: 5) managers, 6) interveners
- Specific specialized services: 7) interveners
- Parents: 8) of children without special needs, and 9) of children with special needs

The present article considers only responses by parents of children with special needs and includes 30 items. To meet the objectives of the present study, however, only eight items (see Appendix A) were used for the descriptive analysis. For three items, parents rated their level of agreement on a Likert-type scale from *strongly disagree* (1) to *strongly agree* (4): “*My experience with my child's inclusion in his/her childcare centre is positive.*” For one item, parents were given three answer choices – *yes*, *no* or *don't know* – regarding the implementation of six educational practices for their child (see Appendix A). For another item, they were asked to answer *yes* or *no*: “*I am asked to participate in the implementation of interventions supporting my child's development within his/her childcare centre.*” For another, they were asked to answer *yes*, *no* or *don't know*: “*I am invited by the childcare centre to participate in training sessions on the inclusion of children with special needs / children with disabilities.*” They rated themselves on a Likert-type scale from *never* (1) to *always* (4) regarding the statement: “*I am aware of the implementation of the recommendations made by the specialized centres encouraging my child's participation in the daily activities of his/her childcare centre.*” Finally, they were asked to answer *yes* or *no* in response to: “*The childcare centre seeks my opinion in identifying my child's developmental needs.*” If the answer was *yes*, they were asked to indicate their level of agreement on a Likert-type scale from *strongly disagree* (1) to *strongly agree* (4).

Analysis

Quantitative data were compiled for analysis using SPSS 26 software. Descriptive analyses (frequencies) were performed to meet the objectives.

Results

To meet the first objective, to determine if parents approved of the adaptation measures implemented in the childcare setting, descriptive statistics were used. To begin, a majority of parents (73.6%) agreed their children with special needs received the support they required in the childcare setting (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Parent's Agreement about their Child with Special Needs' Support in the Childcare Setting

Note. Respondents answered to: “I consider that my child has the support necessary to allow his/her participation in the daily activities of the childcare centre.” The percentages presented represent the frequencies of parents’ response ($N = 76$).

Consistent with the first objective, parents stated that childcare settings also implemented adaptation measures that met a variety of special needs (see Figure 2). In fact, when questioned on this point, over half of parents said their child’s childcare setting adapted the physical environment, available materials, instructions, group activities and individual interventions to respond to the child’s specific needs.

Figure 2*Parents' Comments on the Adaptation Measures Implemented in the Childcare Setting*

Note. Respondents answered to: “My child's childcare centre has introduced measures aimed at adapting” The percentages presented represent the frequencies of parents' response ($N = 76$).

Of these adaptations, those pertaining to individual interventions revealed the biggest difference between parents who said this type of adaptation was carried out (77.6%) compared with those (22.4%) who said it was not. In contrast, a slight difference was observed between parents (48.7%) who said that schedules and routines were adapted compared with those who said they were not (46.1%). Note that, with the exception of adaptations regarding individual interventions, a small proportion (0 to 5.3%) of parents indicated they are not aware if adaptations were implemented in their child's childcare setting.

To meet the second objective, to determine if parents agreed on the identification of their children's developmental needs, descriptive statistics were used. Specifically, almost two-thirds of parents reported they were often (23.7%) or always (40.8%) informed about the implementation of recommendations encouraging their child's participation in activities. When questioned about the identification of their child's developmental needs, three quarters of parents reported that childcare staff asked for their input in this regard. Of these ($n = 57$), 98.3% confirmed that they participated in identifying their child's developmental needs. The parents questioned (67.1%) also reported that childcare staff invited them to help with interventions that supported their child's development. A significant proportion of these parents (84.3%) said they were involved.

To meet the third objective, to determine if parents agreed the inclusion experience for their children was a positive one, descriptive statistics were used. Three-quarters of parents of children

with special needs in inclusive childcare settings who took part in the survey considered their child's experience was positive (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

Parents' Positive Experience Regarding Child's Inclusion in the Childcare Setting

Note. Respondents answered to: “My experience with my child's inclusion in his/her childcare centre is positive.” The percentages presented represent the frequencies of parents' response ($N = 76$).

Discussion

The present study aimed to determine if parents of children with special needs approved of the adaptation measures implemented in the childcare setting, agreed about the identification of their children's developmental needs, and agreed that the inclusion experience for their children was a positive one. Regarding parents' perspective of the practices used in childcare settings, results demonstrated that parents recognized the efforts made for their child. Indeed, the majority believed their child received the support needed to facilitate their participation in the activities offered. As well, over half of parents reported that childcare staff used educational practices that fostered their child's inclusion. Contrary to Lyons et al. (2016), who indicated that childcare staff know too little about children's individual needs to adjust their practices, the parents who took part in our survey said that staff offered their child individualized attention in compliance with the educational program *Accueillir la petite enfance* (MFA, 2019b). In contrast, parents' responses showed that the practices used least apparently concerned the adaptation of schedules and routines as well as the physical environment. This was echoed by the comments of childcare staff, who said that adaptations regarding schedules and routines were those least implemented (Dionne et al., 2020). Results also showed that, with regard to five of six educational practices, a small percentage (1.3% to 5.3%) of parents could not say whether or not adaptations were made.

Parents, certainly, should be informed about the procedures in their child's childcare setting as required by the ministère de la Famille (2019b). Indeed, the vast majority of them appear familiar with the educational practices implemented for their child, a generally positive development, considering that some studies report a lack of communication between parents and staff (Forry et al., 2011; Sheridan et al., 2010; Trivette & Dunst, 2009; Trivette et al., 2010).

Contrary to observations by certain authors (Benson et al., 2008; Ivey, 2004; Starr & Foy, 2001; Stoner et al., 2005), a large majority of parents in the survey reported that the childcare staff asked for their input regarding the identification of their child's developmental needs. What's more, almost all these parents indicated they did so at the request of the staff. This finding is echoed in the comments of Dionne et al. (2014), who showed that parents become involved when targeted interventions are chosen, and in those of Eldar et al. (2010), who likewise confirm the necessity of considering parents' expertise in identifying their child's particular needs to ensure the child receives all the services needed for their inclusion.

The present study has its limitations. First and foremost, it is an exploratory study. Like many studies in the social sciences, it is based on a convenience sample, which means its representativeness is not ensured. This type of sampling was privileged, nevertheless, in order to include participants from whom answers could realistically be obtained. The use of an online questionnaire has limitations as well. In this study, the proportion of respondents with a university degree (more than half) is not representative of the general population and may thus impact the generalizability of the collected data. Accordingly, the Institut national de la recherche scientifique reveals that "several authors mention that those responding to online surveys are usually heavier internet consumers and users, a factor that impacts this type of sample (wealthier, more educated...)" (free translation) (Gingras & Belleau, 2015, p. 4). Furthermore, the rate of uncompleted questionnaires (33%) may reflect the respondents' lack of time or difficulty completing the questionnaire online. Since these data were not used, certain characteristics specific to the reality of these parents may have been overlooked. It would have been interesting to document the reasons for incompleteness so that future projects can be adapted to consider the responses obtained. Additionally, parents having more than one child with special needs attending a childcare setting during the last two years completed only one questionnaire, instead of one per child, which may have resulted in less accuracy. Nevertheless, the majority of parents had only one child with special needs ($n = 60/76$; 79%). Finally, because we did not assess the type of childcare setting attended, we cannot interpret results on this basis. Effectively, the quality of care may be different in profit versus not-for-profit or in-home settings.

Our study's findings indicate that parents' experience regarding the inclusion of their child in the childcare setting is generally positive. It would be relevant, however, to examine parents' perceptions of inclusive practices in parallel with those of the staff to verify possible differences. Future research could also document the use of educational practices based on children's specific needs and the type of childcare setting. Certain child profiles require the implementation of different educational practices. This is especially true for ASD children, for whom visual supports are crucial to their functioning in an inclusive environment (Brodzeller et al., 2018). Finally, it would be worthwhile to further explore if the parents' perspective, when solicited, actually takes into account individualized educational plans, among other things.

In conclusion, it's important that parents of children with special needs share their vision of their child's needs in order to ensure that educational practices employed in the childcare setting are adapted to, and aligned with, at-home practices. To this end, educational practices must be

individualized and welcoming of parental involvement. Because specialized knowledge is essential for childcare professionals, their initial and ongoing training guarantees the quality of the educational practices used with children with special needs.

Key Messages from this Article

Parents of children with special needs. They are encouraged to share their vision of their child's needs so that the educational practices deployed in childcare settings will be more in line with at-home practices.

Professionals. Educational practices must contribute to adapt the environment, support all children, with or without identified special needs, and promote parental involvement. Professional expertise is essential to ensure consistency between educational practices used in the childcare setting and those used in the family setting.

Policymakers. They are advised to introduce amendments promoting the participation of parents and the adaptation of the environment for the better inclusion of all children, with or without special needs.

Messages clés

Parents d'enfants ayant des besoins particuliers : Ils sont encouragés à partager leur vision des besoins de leur enfant afin que les pratiques éducatives déployées dans le milieu de garde soient en cohérence avec les pratiques utilisées à la maison.

Professionnels : Les pratiques éducatives doivent contribuer à adapter l'environnement, à soutenir tous les enfants, avec ou sans besoins particuliers, et à promouvoir la participation des parents. L'expertise des professionnels est essentielle pour assurer la cohérence entre les pratiques éducatives utilisées dans le milieu de garde et celles utilisées dans le milieu familial.

Décideurs : Il leur est conseillé de proposer des ajustements favorisant la participation des parents et l'adaptation de l'environnement pour une meilleure inclusion de tous les enfants, avec ou sans besoins particuliers.

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Appendix A**RESPONDENT: PARENTS OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS / CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES ATTENDING A CHILDCARE CENTRE**

Please complete this questionnaire based on:

- your experience of the last two years;
- the experience that best represents your reality.

- I consider that my child has the support necessary to allow his/her participation in the daily activities of the childcare centre.

Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

- The childcare centre seeks my opinion in identifying my child's developmental needs.

Yes No

If you checked yes, I participate in identifying my child's developmental needs.

Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

- My child's childcare centre has introduced measures aimed at adapting ...:

a) The physical environment to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

b) The material available to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

c) Instructions to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

d) Group activities to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

e) Individual interventions to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

f) The schedule or the routines to his/her needs Yes No Don't know

- My experience with my child's inclusion in his/her childcare centre is positive.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

- I am aware of the implementation of the recommendations made by the specialized centres encouraging my child's participation in the daily activities of his/her childcare centre.
 Never Sometimes Often Always

- I am asked to participate in the implementation of interventions supporting my child's development within his/her childcare centre.
 Yes No

- I am involved in the implementation of interventions supporting my child's development within his/her childcare centre.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

- I am invited by the childcare centre to participate in training sessions on the inclusion of children with special needs / children with disabilities.
 Yes No Don't know